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Research Article

**EFFICACY OF TRANSVAGINAL SONOGRAPHY IN
DIAGNOSIS OF OVARIAN ENDOMETRIOMA**¹Dr Mahnoor Shah, ²Dr Mehwish Niaz, ³Dr Javeria Noreen¹Fatima Jinnah Medical University/Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore²Rai Medical College, Sargodha³Fatima Jinnah Medical University/Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To determine the diagnostic performance of specific ultrasound features in discriminating endometriomas from other adnexal masses.

Study design: A retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020.

Methods: Patients > 25 years of age were included in the study, infertile women with endometriomas who underwent laparotomy or laparoscopy, while patients with pelvic inflammation and ectopic pregnancy were excluded. All patients were prospectively assessed by a transvaginal study. The ultrasound criteria for the diagnosis of endometrioma are: round shaped, cystic structure in adnexa, diffuse low-level internal echoes, multilocularity, hyperechoic wall foci and wall thickness were noted.

Results: Histopathological findings of adnexal mass were endometrioma (n=40), dermoid cyst (n=3), hemorrhagic cyst (n=6), malignancy (n=2) and benign cyst (n=2). Among benign cyst cases of ovarian torsion n=1, broad ligament hematoma n=1, para-tubal cyst n=1, hydrosalpinx n=1 and single functional cyst n=7. The results were analyzed statistically it was found that sensitivity of TVS for diagnosing endometrioma was 86% specificity 90%; the positive predictive value 91% and negative predictive value 98%.

Conclusion: An adnexal mass with diffuse low-level internal echoes and absence of particular neoplastic feature is highly suggestive of endometrioma if multilocularity/hyper echoic wall foci present.

Keywords: TVS, endometrioma, adnexal mass.

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INTRODUCTION:

Endometriosis is the presence of a functional epithelium and stroma of the endometrium in an ectopic position outside the uterus. Endometrioma occurs in 24% of all ovarian cysts. It is debilitating due to the pain and infertility involved. It has a varied ultrasound appearance, ranging from anechoic cysts to echogenic cysts, to masses with multiple septum and solid tissue. Laparoscopy is the gold standard in endometriosis testing for the evaluation of abdominal and pelvic implants, but it can also be used as the primary imaging method in the initial evaluation of suspected gynecological pathology. Ultrasound is also helpful in demonstrating low-level or possibly fluid-level mass with diffuse internal echoes - fluid or residual fluid, or a varied appearance with septum and solid tissue.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore for one-year duration from August 2019 to August 2020. A total of 65 patients were selected from the group of infertile patients. A retrospective study was conducted and the results were statistically evaluated. The study included

patients aged > 25 years, infertile women with endometrioma and endometrioma who underwent laparotomy or laparoscopy, while patients with PID, ectopic pregnancy were excluded from the study. Preoperative transvaginal examination was performed in all patients. All patients were prospectively assessed by a transvaginal study. The ultrasound criteria for the diagnosis of endometrioma are: round shaped, cystic structure in adnexa, diffuse low-level internal echoes, multilocularity, hyperechoic wall foci and wall thickness were noted. Later, the diagnostic features of ultrasound were compared with the histopathological report. All ultrasound features were statistically consistent with the accuracy of diagnosis, severity, specificity, - likelihood factor and + likelihood index.

RESULTS:

Out of 65 patients (n = 40) patients had confirmed endometrioma by histopathology, hemorrhagic cyst (n = 3), malignant neoplasm of dermoid skin (n = 2), severe cyst adenocarcinoma. While n = 11 patients had mild functional cyst problems (n = 7), a patient with ovarian torsion hemorrhagic cyst (n = 1), broad ligament hematoma (n = 1), hydrosalpinx (n = 1) and para-tubal cysts (n = 1).

Table I: Histopathological findings of adnexal mass

Histopathological Findings	=n
Endometrioma	40
Dermoid Cyst	3
Hemorrhagic Cyst	6
Malignancy	2
Benign Cyst	11
Ovarian Torsion	1
Broad Ligament Hematoma	1
Para-tubal Cyst	1
Hydrosalpinx	1
Cyst Simple	7

Table II: Diagnostic performance of ultrasound features in discriminating between endometriomas and non-endometriomas

US. F.	Endomn= 40	Der. n=3	H.Cyst n=6	B.Cyst N=11	Malig n=2	Sen. %	Sp. %	Accur %	-ve L. Ratio	+ve L. Ratio
Cystic Features	38	3	6	11	2	95	19	31	0.3	1
Cyst + thin wall	19	0	4	4	1	48	56	55	0.9	1
Cyst + thick wall	25	0	0	6	1	63	52	54	0.7	1
Cyst. + int. echoe	37	0	5	3	2	93	83	84	0.1	5
L.Levell. Echoe	38	0	3	3	0	95	81	83	0.1	5
L.L.E. no neo+ nofib	26	0	2	0	0	65	96	91	0.4	17
L.L.E., no neo, nowall foci	12	0	0	0	0	30	99	88	0.7	32
L.L.E. no leo., wall foci or multilocularity	18	0	0	0	0	45	99	99	0.6	48
L.L.E. no leo., and multilocularity	12	0	0	0	0	30	100	88	0.7	64

The sensitivity of the vaginal examination in the diagnosis of endometrioma was 86%, specificity 90%, a possible predictive value of 91% and a negative predictive value of 98%. The diagnostic value of each ultrasound feature was assessed separately. When the comparison was made with the histopathological reports and the results of the preoperative ultrasound. It was noted that the most accurate ultrasound features in the diagnosis of endometrioma with 99% accuracy, - probability ratio 0.6, + probability ratio 48, was the presence of a low-level internal echo without wall tuberosity. Accuracy was reduced to 91% when multilocularity was not taken into account, with - probability ratio 0.4, + probability ratio 17, sensitivity 65% and 96%. Similarly, cystic with internal echoes were 84% accurate in recognizing endometrioma with 93% sensitivity, 83% specificity + probability 0.1+ with a probability factor of 5. The wall thickness was also accurately recorded. In the case of thick-walled, the accuracy was only 54%, specificity 52%, sensitivity 65%, + likelihood ratio 1, - likelihood ratio 0.7. However, in the case of thin walls, the accuracy was 55%, specificity 56%, sensitivity 48% - probability coefficient 0.9 and a positive probability factor 1. Accuracy drops strongly to 31% when the ultrasound feature of cystic disease itself was recorded with 95% sensitivity, specificity 19%, + probability index 1, - probability index 0.3 among other cysts.

Graph I: Highest receiver operating characteristic curve for diagnosis of endometrioma by using the ultrasound features

It shows the relationship between specificity and sensitivity. It has the greatest operational cause of the receiver to diagnose endometrioma based on various ultrasound features confirming transvaginal examination as a diagnostic tool for endometriosis.

DISCUSSION:

An ultrasound scan is usually the first test required in patients with clinical symptoms that may suggest pelvic disease. There are a number of definitions of classical endometrioma by experts. Correct reporting and recording of specific ultrasound features help to distinguish between different appendage weights and also serves as important guidelines for patient management. Various studies have also linked the use of transvaginal scanning not only to plasma CA 125 levels but also to another serum tumor marker to obtain accurate diagnosis and to distinguish endometrioma from other ovarian tumors. Similarly, the characteristic blood flow pattern on Doppler examination also distinguishes endometrioma from malignant ovarian cancer. The results of our study show that the overall sensitivity of a vaginal scan to

diagnose endometrioma was 86%, specificity 90%, positive predictive value 91% and negative predictive value 98%. This can be compared with the results of Volpi *et al.* 7, whose study showed the same transvaginal ability to diagnose endometrioma with a sensitivity of 82%, specificity of 97%, predictive value + and - 94% and 92%, respectively. The presence of low-level echoes is a uniform diagnosis for different examinations, while the thickness and contour of the wall as well as shape and position differ between examinations. Understanding the extent to which any particular feature or set of features increases or decreases the likelihood of a diagnosis of endometrioma is important as this knowledge can be used to steer the judgment towards identifying those features that matter most and avoid effort and confusion in characterizing those features

that don't matter. Alcazar et al. (8) found a positive probability coefficient of 9.8 and a negative probability of 0.1 in contrast to 27 endometriomas from 55 other adnexal tumors by "the presence of a circular homogeneous low-level hypoechoic echo mass". The same results were comparable to our study because the low-echo cyst result had 84% accuracy + a likelihood factor of 5 and a likelihood factor of 0.1. 95% of endometriomas show a low level of internal echo, while only the cystic ultrasound feature did not improve the diagnostic results. Foci of the hyperechoic wall gave a positive probability factor of 6.2. Various studies show that a hemorrhagic cyst also has a low-level echo without hyperechoic or areas with heterogenic echogenicity. Follow-up helps to make an accurate diagnosis, unlike our study with 55% accuracy, 48% sensitivity, 56% specificity + probability ratio of 1. Our study showed LLE, multilocularity, thin walls with foci but no tuberosity, 99% accuracy, specificity 99%, sensitivity 45%, - probability factor 0.6 and + probability factor 48, which can be easily compared with studies showing that patients with wall nodularity and focal impedance can predict ovarian cancer that may benefit from ultrasound / Color Doppler MRI or both for further evaluation and treatment.

CONCLUSION:

An adnexal mass with diffuse low-level internal echoes and absence of particular neoplastic features is highly suggestive of endometrioma if multilocularity or hyper echoic wall foci are present. A patient with a mass with diffuse low-level echoes and other ultrasound features may benefit from additional imaging.

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